

Cultural practises contributing to gender-based violence (GBV) in Igbo land: An exploration of Buchi Emecheta's *The Bride Price*.

This paper examines how embedded cultural norms generate power imbalances and sustain gender-based violence (GBV) against Igbo women and girls. Despite governmental efforts to curb violence in Nigeria, implementation gaps persist, particularly within Igbo communities. The study attributes this failure partly to the state's reluctance to confront harmful cultural practices, notably marriage customs such as bride price, which reinforce feminine commodification. Focusing on Buchi Emecheta's *The Bride Price* (1976), the paper analyses how patriarchal ideology and cultural expectations intersect to normalise violence. Through context-based character analysis, it explores the experiences of Aku-nna and Ma Blackie as women navigating culturally sanctioned oppression. Anchored in Ogunyemi's African womanist framework, the study demonstrates how social norms restrict female agency, limit educational and economic opportunities, and legitimise physical, emotional, and sexual abuse. It argues that African women's writing reclaims literary space as resistance, exposing the psychological and social consequences of GBV while informing gender advocacy and social transformation in Igbo society.

Keywords: African feminism; bride price; gender-based violence; Igbo culture; patriarchy; power imbalance

Introduction

Gender-based violence (GBV) encompasses any form of abuse—physical or emotional—that disproportionately affects women and girls in specific social contexts. For proper contextualisation and analysis, this paper adopts a robust and comprehensive definition of GBV as any act of abuse (physical, emotional or sexual):

That results in or is likely to result in physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivations of liberty whether occurring in public or private life. It includes physical, sexual and psychological violence occurring in the family, in the community, or perpetuated by the state. It includes battering, sexual abuse of female children, dowry-related violence, marital rape, female genital mutilation and other traditional practices harmful to women (United Nations' 1993 Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women)

Conceptualised in this way, GBV constitutes harmful practices that threaten the well-being and holistic development of women and girls, violating their fundamental human rights. These acts are deeply embedded in cultural traditions and social institutions, maintained through unequal power

relations, rigid gender norms, and ideological structures that legitimise women's subordination, while also eroding social cohesion and undermining the overall fabric of society. While the UN definition provides a global framework, research indicates that local norms and values shape how this violence is experienced, producing harmful practices that compromise women's dignity and hinder societal development (Ezenwa-Ohaeto, 2024; Okpokwasili, 2024). Within Igbo society, these norms are entwined with patriarchy, which positions men at the helm of social, economic, and political affairs, granting them authority, privilege, and agency.

Over the last three decades, the Nigerian government has taken steps to eliminate discrimination against women and girls, including the enactment of the National Gender Policy (NGP), which promotes equity, justice, and sustainable development. However, implementation remains a challenge due to "deep-rooted cultural norms, systemic discrimination, and limited opportunities hindering the progress of women and other marginalised gender groups" (Ayamba, Ekom, Bassey and Ekpo, 2024:84). These norms, which perpetuate violence and oppression, operate within patriarchal frameworks. Patriarchy sets "parameters for women [and girls] structurally unequal positions in families and markets by condoning domestic and sexual violence" (Atim, 2017:74). It legitimises women and girls' marginalisation in private and public spheres. Consequently, culture and patriarchy intersect to generate and sustain practices that regulate GBV against Igbo women and girls. Evidence shows that Igbo women experience pervasive violence due to hierarchical arrangements embedded in traditional social structures (Ezedinanchi and Iwuchukwu, 2025), illustrated by marriage and naming conventions, widowhood rites and female disinheritance. This study examines how female novelists of Igbo descent, specifically, Buchi Emecheta articulates their views about how these practices influence feminine experiences in Igbo land.

To this end, this paper contextually analyses how *Aku-nna* and *Ma Blackie* in *The Bride Price* (1976), navigate the terrains of their patriarchal society. Accordingly, the study poses two research questions: (1) How do embedded cultural norms shape power relations in postcolonial African contexts? And (2) What literary stylistics does Emecheta employ in *The Bride Price* to demonstrate the normalisation and perpetuation of GBV in Igbo society? Through contextual analysis and close reading, the paper demonstrates how Emecheta foregrounds the ways cultural practices constrain female agency, producing multiple forms of abuse. Anchored in Chikwenye Okonjo Ogunyemi's African womanist framework, the study highlights the structural and cultural mechanisms through

which Igbo society perpetuates violence against women and girls, offering a lens for interrogating systemic inequality and the marginalisation of women. By centring the voices and experiences of Aku-nna and Ma Blackie in *The Bride Price*, the paper provides indigenously grounded insights into how socially ingrained beliefs about gender identity and roles sustain GBV. Beyond illustrating oppression, it underscores the role of Igbo female novelists in using literature as a site of representation, reconstruction, and critical negotiation of cultural norms.

Background to the Study

Igbo society, one of Nigeria's three major ethnic groups, is located in the southeastern region of the country and is characterised by a rich cultural heritage informed by a distinct worldview and philosophical tradition. Central to this worldview is the Igbo conception of personhood, which emphasises relationality. As Onwuatuegwu (2023:41) explains, personhood in Igbo philosophy “is not solely defined by individual attributes, but it is a relational concept that is shaped by one's interactions with others and the world around them.” This relational understanding of human identity has significant implications for the construction of gender identities and roles, as social value and legitimacy are negotiated within communal structures rather than individual autonomy. Within this framework, patriarchy functions as a dominant organising principle, shaping social hierarchies and allocating authority, power, and agency along gendered lines.

The patriarchal orientation of Igbo society legitimises women and girls' subordination and by so doing, contributes to the normalisation of gender-based violence (GBV) against women and girls. These acts of injustices and oppression manifest through practices - such as bride price, female disinheritance, and widowhood rites- which eventually pre-empt material and symbolic violence. Situated within Nigeria's culturally diverse landscape, this study focuses on Igbo society, where empirical research indicates persistently high levels of GBV. Within this social landscape, Molokwu and Uchime (2023:155) observe that southeastern Nigeria records the highest prevalence of gender-based violence in the country, despite decades of advocacy, legal reform, and policy interventions. This persistence underscores the difficulty of dismantling culturally sanctioned forms of violence and highlights the limitations of rights-based frameworks that fail to engage adequately with Indigenous belief systems.

Beyond individual harm, GBV constitutes a violation of women's fundamental human rights and generates far-reaching social and developmental consequences that extend from private households into the public sphere. The endurance of GBV in African societies poses a significant challenge to global and continental development agendas, particularly the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5), which seeks to achieve gender equality and empower women and girls by 2030. Similarly, the African Union's Agenda 2063 envisions "an integrated, prosperous and peaceful Africa, driven by its own citizens," with Aspiration 6 emphasising people-driven development that harnesses the potential of women and youth. However, patriarchy remains a principal obstacle to the realisation of these goals. In the Igbo context, patriarchy is not merely a colonial inheritance but also an Indigenous ideology that structures social consciousness and everyday practice. As Makama (2013:115) argues, patriarchy "reduces womanhood to a mere infidel and a second-class citizen," confining women to unpaid and undervalued roles as daughters, wives, and mothers. These roles are socially learned, internalised, and reproduced across generations, reinforcing power asymmetries that normalise female marginalisation and victimisation.

Such ideological dispositions are further reflected in public discourse and political culture. Former Nigerian President Muhammadu Buhari's 2016 remark that his wife "belongs to my kitchen, and my living room and the other room" exemplifies how patriarchal values continue to legitimise the relegation of women's agency to the domestic sphere. Statements of this nature reveal the extent to which gender inequality is sustained not only through cultural practice but also through symbolic and discursive forms of power. Against this backdrop, this paper undertakes a close reading of Buchi Emecheta's *The Bride Price*, focusing on the experiences of Aku-nna and Ma Blackie. Anchored in Chikwenye Okonjo Ogunyemi's African womanist framework, the study situates these characters' encounters with GBV within culturally and historically specific structures of oppression, while also foregrounding strategies of endurance, negotiation, and resistance. By examining how Indigenous ideology intersects with patriarchal norms in the text, the paper offers a culturally grounded lens for understanding gendered violence and contributes to broader debates on agency, representation, and resistance in African literary scholarship.

Statement of the Problem

In Igbo society, GBV persists as a social issue rooted in complex patriarchal dynamics. It manifests in both sexual and physical forms and is normalised through cultural practices such as bride price and naming conventions, which reinforce the passive and subordinate positioning of women and girls. In this sense, GBV functions as a culturally sanctioned performance of behaviour regulated by societal expectations. Despite extensive global research on violence against women and its implications for development, a significant gap remains in studies that integrate Indigenous perspectives and voices. African feminist scholars argue that the limitations of such research stem from analytical frameworks that are detached from local realities, thereby underscoring the need for culturally grounded lenses that speak directly to the lived experiences of specific African societies.

Using a qualitative, context-based approach grounded in character analysis, this study examines Aku-nna and Ma Blackie in *The Bride Price*. Through these character portrayals, the paper demonstrates how traditional gender roles, patriarchal ideologies, and beliefs in masculine superiority and feminine inferiority contribute to the normalisation of violence against women and girls in Igbo society. Addressing GBV in Igbo society requires a well-defined approach that acknowledges the socioeconomic and cultural factors while promoting gender equality, unrestricted access to quality education, affordable healthcare and economic empowerment. This study, therefore, aims to delve deeper into how these socioeconomic and cultural dynamics influence the perpetuation of GBV in Igbo society.

This paper explores how GBV is constructed and performed in African social units. It posits that the process is birthed in family units through a gender initiation at birth, a performance reinforced by peculiar naming conventions. According to Ekwueme (2025:1), GBV manifests in ways “that promote patriarchy, reducing women to second-class citizens,” leaving them with no space of their own. One principal actor in this space is the man whose role it is to ensure that the woman learns from birth to perform her identity as spelt out in the cultural code of conduct. The analysis reveals how patriarchal norms produce feminine vulnerability. It also highlights strategies through which women resist, renegotiate, and reconfigure these constraints. By centring Igbo women’s voices, the study positions literature as a critical site for feminist theorising, knowledge reconstruction, and social advocacy.

Research Aims

This study explores how cultural norms and entrenched patriarchal principles contribute to GBV within Igbo society, using literary depictions of female characters as its primary lens. The focus is on Aku-nna and Ma Blackie in *The Bride Price*. By examining the interplay between cultural norms, traditional practices, and societal expectations regarding gender identity and roles, this paper illuminates how culture perpetuates violence against women and girls. The two primary aims of this research are:

1. To examine how Emecheta depicts the ways Igbo cultural norms and practices perpetuate gender-based violence against women and girls;
2. To analyse how African literature functions as a site of renegotiation, resistance, and representation for Igbo women navigating tenebrous cultural terrains in Igbo society.

Research Questions

1. How does Emecheta in *The Bride Price* depict how Igbo cultural norms and patriarchal practices constrain women's agency and produce violence?
2. In what ways do literary texts like *The Bride Price* function as sites of renegotiation and resistance for Igbo women navigating gendered crises?

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study pays attention to how culture, patriarchy and societal expectations intersect to normalise gender-based violence (GBV) in Igbo society. It clarifies four interrelated concepts—culture, norms, gender, and patriarchy—and demonstrates how their interaction structures women's lived experiences within Igbo sociocultural contexts. Idang (2015:98) defines culture as “the patterned way of life shared by a particular group of people that claims to share a single origin or descent,” with unique beliefs, values, customs, traditions and beliefs that influence their dressing, religious beliefs and overarching worldview. In short, culture encompasses all the idiosyncrasies that influence the perceptions and actions of a people. Among the Igbo people of the southeastern part of Nigeria, these practices include marriage and widowhood rituals, among others. It is important to note that these practices are framed by social

norms, specifically, those that allocate power, voice, and agency to men, while positioning women and girls as subordinate.

Norms are socially constructed and codified rules of conduct that regulate behaviour, evaluate actions, and shape perceptions of society and socialisation patterns. They influence people's actions, motives, and traits and function as moral signposts within the community. As Nmah, Abalogu and Anahalu (2024:38) observe, norms “are set patterns or codes of behaviour [that] constitute the moral values in Igbo land.” Within this framework, norms operate as the mechanism through which cultural values are internalised and through which gender identities are learnt, enacted, and sustained. Gender, therefore, is treated as a social construct shaped through repeated performances. It is conceptualised as the “societal differences and relations between men and women which are learned [and mastered through constant performances]” (Uche, Nwabanne, and Adejuwon, 2025:115). These gendered relations are produced and reinforced by ideological, historical, religious, ethnic, and cultural forces anchored in patriarchy.

Patriarchy functions here as an organising principle that enforces normative gender performances and regulates access to power, resources, and authority. Walby (1989:214) defines it as “a system of social structures and practices in which men dominate, oppress and exploit women,” while Umunakwe (2018:283) describes it as a “culturally endorsed, ontologically certified [and] politically accepted [frame that legitimises] the gross restriction of women's [...] right to power and possession.” For women and girls socialised primarily for marriage and childbearing, patriarchal practices produce structured inequalities and heightened vulnerability. This supports the assertion that patriarchy constrains and justifies feminine autonomy and agency, normalising masculine domination and the perpetuation of violent acts. By focusing on the intersection of culture, patriarchy and societal expectation, this conceptual framework foregrounds the need to interrogate entrenched cultural beliefs that sustain patriarchal power, while also pointing to the possibility of mobilising cultural resources to promote women's empowerment, equity, and sustainable development within Igbo-centric contexts.

Patriarchy perpetuates violence against women and girls by legitimising inequality and normalising domination. By restricting women's autonomy and access to education, healthcare, resources, and economic opportunities, these practices undermine gender equality and feminine

agency. Culture thus functions as a causal force linking patriarchal ideology to GBV and, ultimately, to stalled development. This conceptual framework foregrounds the need to interrogate entrenched cultural beliefs that sustain patriarchal power, while also pointing to the possibility of mobilising cultural resources to promote women's empowerment, equity, and sustainable development within Igbo-centric contexts.

Theoretical Framework

In this paper, GBV in Igbo society is analysed using the African womanist theory. Within the African feminist framework, there are different feminisms that directly speak to the experiences of African women; some of these are motherism, nego-feminism, snail-sense feminism, to mention a few. However, Ogunyemi's framework is adopted here because it centres African women's lived experiences, cultural specificity, and strategies of survival and resistance. As Ogunyemi (1985:63-64) notes, African womanism:

Explores the gamut of other positions [...] producing an exciting, fluid corpus that defies rigid categorisation. More often than not, where a white woman writer may be a feminist, a black woman writer is likely to be a 'womanist'. That is, she will recognise that along with her consciousness of sexual issues, she must incorporate racial, cultural, national, economic and political considerations into her philosophy.

The emphasis on culturally grounded, intersectional consciousness makes African womanism particularly suited to examining GBV in Igbo society, where patriarchal norms are deeply embedded in everyday life. These experiences are shaped by cultural practices—such as naming rituals and marriage customs—that institutionalise gender hierarchies and violate women's rights and dignity. Patriarchy functions as a central mechanism enforcing these norms, producing structural inequalities that restrict women's access to autonomy, resources, and protection. In *The Bride Price*, Aku-nna's compliance with the bride price system demonstrates how culturally sanctioned practices reproduce subordination: she accepts that the bride price she generates will fund her brother's education, subordinating her aspirations to patriarchal family expectations (Emecheta, 1976:52). This insight positions African womanism as a framework capable of connecting cultural practices, patriarchal ideology, and GBV in Igbo society. It illuminates how entrenched social structures sustain violence against women while also highlighting spaces for

resistance, negotiation, and empowerment, providing a fully indigenously grounded lens for analysing gendered crises in literature and society.

Significance of the Study

Although several studies address GBV in Igbo society, a significant gap remains in scholarship examining how the African womanist frame explicates this issue. This gap is evident in studies that fail to integrate Western theoretical models with Igbo-centred worldviews in the analysis of Igbo literary texts that explore how deeply-rooted cultural structures subordinate women and girls. As such, this study contributes to discourses on gender-based violence, specifically, as it relates to the Igbo woman, as replicated through the portrayals of Aku-nna and Ma Blackie in *The Bride Price*. Drawing on Ogunyemi's theoretical frame, the study demonstrates how socially constructed identities produce conditions that expose women to violence and death. This study has important implications for academics and policy-makers because it highlights why gender-based violence continues to be a persistent concern, demonstrating the role of African literature as a critical site of representation by drawing parallels between fictional narratives and the lived experiences of women in contemporary societies.

Research Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative, interpretive research approach that combines analytical and exploratory designs. An interpretive framework is particularly suitable as it regulates how actions, meanings, and experiences are examined within the purposively selected text, *The Bride Price*. This text is analysed as a cultural narrative that reflects and interrogates gender-based violence (GBV) within Igbo society. The textual analysis is complemented by peer-reviewed secondary scholarship on African feminisms, indigenous epistemological frameworks, and resistance to gendered oppression within Igbo sociocultural contexts. The study employs close textual reading supported by character analysis to examine representations of oppression, exploitation, and marginalisation, with particular attention to female characters whose lived realities are shaped by

patriarchal ideology and rigid cultural norms. Narrative development and sociocultural context are examined to reveal how literature both reproduces and contests dominant gender ideologies.

The analytical framework is anchored in Ogunyemi's African womanist theory. This theoretical framework provides an indigenously grounded lens for understanding how culturally ascribed meanings of gender produce precarious conditions that expose women and girls to violence and vulnerability, while also illuminating strategies through which women renegotiate and reconfigure identity within constrained sociocultural spaces (Ogunyemi, 1985). By centring indigenous experiences, epistemologies, and feminist strategies of survival and resistance, the study foregrounds socially induced vulnerability and unequal exposure to harm, positioning African literature as a critical site for feminist knowledge production and for analysing how gendered crises are produced and contested in Igbo sociocultural settings.

Delimitation

This paper analyses how Emecheta and Adichie portray females in *The Bride Price*. Particular attention is given to characters whose experiences give shape to the plot of the texts – Aku-nna and Ma Blackie in *The Bride Price*, whose roles as daughters, wives, and mothers structure the narratives. This will enable the study to carry out a comprehensive analysis of how culture perpetuates violence in the Igbo sociocultural setting. This paper utilises a unique theoretical framework that integrates the Indigenous lens of Ogunyemi, thereby disrupting the notion of universal worldviews and experiences. It should be noted that this paper does not aspire to be a complete socioeconomic, cultural and historical treatise on violence against women and girls; in a sense, it concentrates on *The Bride Price* as a literary treatment of how cultural practices perpetuate GBV in Igbo sociocultural settings.

Contextualisation

This paper points in one direction - the repositioning of the Igbo woman from the margin to the centre, where she actively participates in developing her society. In this space, the woman is empowered to challenge and negate the patriarchal notion of inferiority and passivity, representing her identity as a vocal and active individual. This can only be achieved through the provision of access to quality education and other mediums of financial empowerment. To establish the premise

of this argument, this section starts with brief synopses of *The Bride Price* focusing on how culture continuously perpetuates violence in Igbo society.

First published in 1976, *The Bride Price* explores the themes of culture, tradition and gender roles within the context of Igbo society. It can be read as a semi-autobiographical novel that explores the cultural dynamics that influence the perpetuation of GBV in hierarchically constructed Igbo-centric families. *The Bride Price* revolves around Aku-nna, the first and only daughter of Ezekiel Odia and his wife, Ma Blackie, and elder sister to Nna-nndo, a girl whose life unfolds amid the sociocultural and political turmoil marking the beginning of the British colonial administration in Nigeria. Originally from Ibuza, an Igbo community in southeastern Nigeria, Ezekiel and Ma Blackie Odia settle in Lagos, an emerging metropolitan centre. Although Ezekiel and his family are Christian converts, this religious affiliation does not displace their adherence to traditional belief systems. This is evident when the ailing Ezekiel sends his wife to “Ibuza to placate their Oboshi river goddess into giving her some babies” (Emecheta, 1976:8). During Ma Blackie’s absence, Ezekiel dies. She returns shortly after his burial, and the family—referred to as Ezekiel’s movable property—Ma Blackie, Aku-nna, and Nna-nndo, are loaded into a lorry and taken back to Ibuza.

This return enables Ma Blackie to mourn - a man who married her as a child bride, taunted her for bearing only one son after paying an exorbitant bride price, and cut a lock of her hair to “ensure that [she] would always be his” (Emecheta, 1976:71) - for nine full moons. After the mourning period, Okonkwo, Ezekiel’s brother, inherits Ma Blackie in accordance with customary practice. She conceives shortly after. Meanwhile, Aku-nna and Nna-nndo begin attending the village school. It is here that Aku-nna develops a close relationship with her teacher, Chike Ofulue. Their growing attachment attracts social disapproval because of Chike’s ancestry. Upon reaching puberty and completing her education, Aku-nna elopes with Chike to Ughelli. This decision destabilises her family and provokes Okonkwo’s intense resentment. In his anger, he “made a small doll in the exact image of Aku-nna and pierced the heart of the doll with a needle” (Emecheta, 1976:156). In Ughelli, Aku-nna and Chike settle into marriage. She becomes pregnant but dies shortly after giving birth to a frail baby girl, whom she names Joy.

Aku-nna's death is interpreted through two explanatory frameworks. The first attributes it to physical factors, suggesting that she was malnourished and medically unfit for pregnancy. The second explanation situates her death within a cultural logic, linking it to her marriage to a man whose bride price was never paid. Although the former appears medically plausible, the latter is accorded greater cultural authority. This belief reinforces a long-standing social edict:

Old taboos of the land. If a girl wished to live long and see her children's children, she must accept the husband chosen for her by her people, and the bride price must be paid. If the bride price was not paid, she would never survive the birth of her first child. (Emecheta, 1976:168)

This narrative synopsis provides a foundation for examining how cultural norms regulate and shape gendered performances, particularly those of women and girls who are oppressed within patriarchal social systems. Such oppression is socially constructed, learned, and internalised through the interactions and expectations of community members. This is reflective of a “disorientative behaviour or signs of neurosis in the female character is indicative of the unsureness of a steady life for the girl-child in patriarchal African society” (Odiye, 2019:42). Through this portrayal, Emecheta exposes the structural systems of GBV inherent in Igbo families. The next section explores this process in detail, unpacking how social practices shape gender-based violence in Igbo society.

Cultural Practices that Influence GBV in Igbo society

A defining feature of African womanist literature is its grounding in the lived experiences of women constrained by patriarchy, often functioning as protest against sociocultural practices that hinder both the girl-child and broader societal development (Igbolo and Ejue, 2016). In *The Bride Price*, Emecheta situates her female characters within the material realities of patriarchal dominance and oppressive cultural dictates. Aku-nna, though academically gifted, recognises that she “would have to marry, and that the bride price she would fetch would help to pay the school fees for her brother Nna-nndo” (Emecheta, 1976:52). Her acceptance underscores the structural limitations imposed on Igbo girls, whose agency is circumscribed by entrenched patriarchal propositions. This discussion, therefore, examines how culturally sanctioned practices—marriage, bride price, early marriage, naming conventions, socialisation, and widowhood rites—function as

interlocking mechanisms that sustain gender-based violence (GBV) within Igbo sociocultural contexts.

In Igbo society, marriage constitutes a central institution through which both social cohesion and patrilineal authority are maintained. It is not merely a private union but a socially regulated framework oriented towards procreation, lineage continuity, and communal responsibility. Isidenu (2015:123) defines marriage as the “lawfully living together of a man with his wife or wives with the aim of begetting children who will be trained in an acceptable manner as required by the customs.” Anedo and Anedo (2017:70) similarly observe that once consummated, a wife is incorporated not only into her husband’s life but into his extended kinship network. Contemporary scholarship reiterates this communal framing, describing marriage as foundational to family and society (Sulaimon, 2024:2) and as a collective alliance between families and communities (Nwokedi, Felix-Joe, and Ofoeze, 2025:297). Within this network, women’s autonomy is systematically subordinated to collective expectations, which prioritise lineage continuity over individual agency.

Marriage is simultaneously a site of economic regulation. Central to this is the practice of bride price, defined as the “material or monetary token given by the groom and his family to the bride’s family as a sign of gratitude, honour and commitment” (Nwokedi, Felix-Joe and Ofoeze, 2025:298). Beyond its symbolic framing, bride price functions as a mechanism of patriarchal authority, structuring women’s labour, reproductive capacity, and domestic obligations within patrilineal networks. The symbolic and material dimensions are mutually reinforcing: it legitimises unions in communal and spiritual terms, while simultaneously converting the bride’s body and labour into a form of lineage capital. Obi-Nwosu (2020) notes that this practice consolidates power imbalances, positioning women as secondary citizens whose rights are subordinated to marital and extended family hierarchies. In *The Bride Price*, Ezekiel Ochia’s payment of “double the normal bride price” for Ma Blackie amplifies expectations of fertility, rendering her failure to produce more than one son a source of shame: “what had he to show for it all—an only son!” (Emecheta, 1976:9). Such exchanges illuminate the intersection of symbolic honour and material control, demonstrating how culturally sanctioned practices can normalise entitlement to female bodies and labour.

Early girl-child marriage exemplifies the coercive dimensions of these practices. Defined as “any marriage carried out below the age of 18 years before the girl is physically, physiologically and psychologically ready to shoulder the responsibilities of marriage and childbearing” (Atim, 2017:76), such unions expose girls to premature pregnancy, curtailed education, and increased vulnerability to physical and sexual abuse. Within this framework, bride price legitimises early marriage by signalling the transfer of reproductive and domestic labour. Aku-nna’s experiences illustrate this vulnerability: her education is subordinated to family expectations, while marital obligations circumscribe her agency.

The structural logic that positions women as exchangeable in marriage is embedded from birth through naming and early socialisation. These practices, like other social performances, are learned within the family, “the most fundamental social unit and bedrock of society” (Enwo-Irem, 2025:175). Through daily interactions, hierarchical power relations are internalised: fathers assume authority, while mothers and daughters are oriented toward marriage and childbearing. Patrilineal ideology reinforces this hierarchy, holding that “the male child guarantees the continuity of the family lineage and provides security for parents at old age” (Iherue, 2020:26). Names act as semiotic markers of social expectation, signalling roles and responsibilities from birth. Mensha () describes names as labels of identity that Völkel, Ndlovu, and Nassenstein (2023:145) describe names as a “fundamental linguistic and semiotic phenomenon” shaped by cultural context. The meanings of the characters, Aku-nna— father’s wealth—explicitly marks her as an economic and reproductive asset, while Nna-nndo—father is shelter—encodes dependency and male centrality. Together, naming conventions and early socialisation naturalise gender hierarchies and prepare the ideological ground for women’s later commodification in marriage.

Within this cultural matrix, girls internalise submissive femininity that is later enacted and reinforced in marriage. Ngcobo (1988:141) observes that girls are socialised to marry and bear children to fulfil womanhood, and that bride price “gives exclusive sexual rights to the man.” This internalisation produces normative expectations that rationalise physical, emotional, and sexual control within intimate partnerships. Oluko and Abasuekong (2024:47) define Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) as abuse occurring within romantic relationships, encompassing physical, sexual, emotional abuse and controlling behaviour. In *The Bride Price*, Aku-nna’s experiences—first with

Okoboshi and later as Chike's young wife—illustrate the heightened vulnerability produced by early marriage, socialised obedience, and bride price obligations.

Widowhood constitutes a further stage in the life-cycle through which patriarchal authority is maintained. In Igbo cosmology, the living and the dead are interconnected, rendering widows ritually impure upon their husbands' deaths. Oreh (2015:6) describes widowhood as a sudden and devastating rupture, marked by restrictive practices including seclusion, hair shaving, disenfranchisement from inheritance, and socioeconomic decline. These practices are not merely ceremonial but enforce structural violence, sustaining male control beyond the grave. In *The Bride Price*, Ma Blackie's widowhood begins with confinement and an extended mourning period:

Stay and mourn for her dead husband for nine full moons... Once a man had taken this step, his wife would never leave him... and as such a woman, if the husband died, must mourn for nine moons (Emecheta, 1976:71).

Her forced relocation to Ibuza with her late husband's "movable property"—including her children—exemplifies widowhood inheritance as an extension of patriarchal ownership, erasing agency and reinforcing economic dispossession. Across the life cycle—from naming and childhood socialisation to marriage, reproduction, and widowhood—Igbo cultural institutions collectively reproduce hierarchical gender relations. Men are constructed as providers, lineage bearers, and decision-makers; women as dependants whose identities are tied to domesticity and fertility. These roles are not incidental but systematically produced through familial instruction, communal validation, and ritual enforcement. Marriage and bride price symbolise legitimacy and continuity while institutionalising power asymmetries that normalise GBV. Early marriage truncates girlhood; bride price commodifies female bodies; naming conventions and socialisation inscribe hierarchical expectations; and widowhood rites regulate and punish women's autonomy.

Taken together, these practices reveal a continuum of structural inequality embedded within Igbo sociocultural organisation. By tracing these mechanisms through *The Bride Price*, Emecheta exposes how cultural norms—while framed as tradition, honour, or communal stability—operate as enduring structures that legitimise and sustain gender-based violence.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that patriarchal ideology and embedded cultural norms intersect to sustain gender-based violence (GBV) in Igbo society. Violence is not incidental but structurally produced within a system that privileges male authority and marginalises women and girls based on gender. Practices such as early marriage, bride price, naming conventions, and widowhood inheritance function as institutional mechanisms that reproduce unequal power relations and normalise women's subordination across the life cycle. The persistence of these practices underscores the limitations of policy frameworks that fail to confront the cultural foundations of inequality. Addressing GBV within Igbo contexts, therefore, requires robust policy implementation instruments that centralise women and girls. These include community-based gender education programmes, culturally responsive legal enforcement mechanisms, protection and support services for survivors, gender-sensitive judicial processes, and economic empowerment initiatives that enhance women's autonomy. Integrating Indigenous knowledge systems with rights-based approaches can further strengthen implementation. Such instruments must move beyond symbolic reform to transformative engagement with patriarchal norms, ensuring that women and girls are positioned not as passive beneficiaries but as active agents in social, cultural, and institutional change.

References

Agbor Igbolo, M. and Ejue, F. U. (2016). Socio-cultural factors and practices affecting the girl child among the Annang people of Akwa Ibom State, *Studies in Media and Communication*, 4(2), pp. 125–143.

Atim, G. (2017). Girls not brides: Ending child marriage in Nigeria, *Journal of Gender, Information and Development in Africa (JGIDA)*, 6, pp. 73–94.

Ayamba, I. A., Ekom, B. E., Bassey, U. S. and Ekpo, O. O. (n.d.). National gender policy in Nigeria: Uncovering the core issues, *Socialscientia: Journal of the Social Sciences and Humanities*, pp. 84–94.

Bruno, U. O. (n.d.). Philosophical mediation between patriarchal theory and feminism: A reflection on Igbo society, in Okocha, D. O., Yousaf, M. and Onobe, M. J. (eds.) *Handbook of Research on Deconstructing Culture and Communication in the Global South*. Chapter 18, pp. 283–295.

Ekwueme, S. C. (2025). Empirical evaluation of the role of African traditional religion in promoting gender-based violence in Southeast Nigeria, *Religions*, 16, pp. 1–21.

Emecheta, B. (1976) *The Bride Price*. New York: George Braziller.

Enwo-Irem, I. N. (2025). Family and parenting in transition: Exploring changes in parenting in Igbo lifestyle up to the 21st century, *UNIZIK Journal of History and International Studies*, 11(1), pp. 175–185.

Ezenwa-Ohaeto, N. (2024). Promoting cultural shifts: A humanistic focus on practices that undermine women’s dignity, rights and societal advancement, *Preorgess*, 4.

Idang, G. E. (2015). African culture and values, *Phronimon*, 16, pp. 97–111.

Isidienu, I. C. (2015). The family as the bedrock of Igbo traditional society, *JMEL – Journal of Modern European Languages and Literatures*, 4, pp. 119–128.

Makama, G. A. (2013). Patriarchy and gender inequality in Nigeria: The way forward’, *European Scientific Journal*, 9, pp. 115–143.

Molokwu, U. C. and Uchime, V. O. (2020) ‘Traditional religion, Christianity and gender-based violence among Igbo women of Southeastern Nigeria, 1980–2015, *Preorc Journal of Gender and Sexuality Studies*, 1, pp. 155–179.

Ngcobo, L. (1988). African motherhood – Myth and reality, in Holst Petersen, K. (ed.) *Criticism and Ideology*. Uppsala: Nordiska Afrikainstitutet, pp. 141–154.

Nmah, P. E., Abalogu, D. M. and Anahalu, G. A. (2024). Re-evaluation of norms and value system deterioration among Igbo youth in a digitalised society: The way forward, *ESTAGA Journal of Philosophy, Arts and Humanities (EJOPAAH)*, 1(1), pp. 37–46.

Nwokedi, G. O., Felix-Joe, C. J. and Ofoeze, M. I. (2025). An evaluation of the socio-cultural implications of high bride-price on youth in Mbano, Imo State, *Jos Journal of Religion and Philosophy*, 6(2), pp. 297–314.

Obi-Nwosu, H. (2017). Gender roles in Igbo culture: An overview, *Zik Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3, pp. 44–55.

Odinye, I. E. (2019). Fleshing out memory through feminist consciousness: Psychoanalyzing violent girlhood experiences in Buchi Emecheta’s *The Bride Price*, *IGWEBUIKE: An African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 5(3), pp. 41–60.

Okpokwasili, O. (2024). Gender-based violence: A barrier to achieving human rights and sustainable development goals in Nigeria, *AKU*, 5(2), pp. 92–106.

Uche, M. C., Nwabanne, I. C. and Adejuwon, R. T. (2025). Gender and language in Nigeria: A religio-cultural approach, *Journal of Igbo Language, Literature, Culture, and Religious Studies*, 1(1), pp. 112–119.

United Nations (1993) United Nations Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women 1993 [Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women | OHCHR](#). Accessed January 31, 2026.

Walby, S. (1989). Theorising patriarchy, *Sociology*, 23, pp. 213–234.

Onyema, I. S. (2020). Moral perspective of male child preference in traditional Igbo society, 9(2), pp. 25–43.

Ogunyemi, C. O. (1985). Womanism: The dynamics of the contemporary Black female novel in English, *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, 11, pp. 63–80.